

EMPLOYEE VOICE UNLOCKS PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT

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ABSTRACT

The study aims to understand the relationship of Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and the organization's commitment to several public and private banks in Punjab state. In today's world of globalization and liberalization these three variables are extremely valuable to any organization and can contribute to performance as well as to competitive advantage. If fairness regarding the procedures of the organization is perceived by the employees, they tend to develop a sense of satisfaction towards their respective jobs as well as commitment towards their organization. The times when innovation and sustainable development are the buzz words in organizations, these three variables are necessary to develop human resources. The aim of this research project is to enhance the understanding if interrelationship does exist between these variables.

Keywords : Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice, Organization Commitment, Competitive Advantage

1. INTRODUCTION

Procedural fairness refers to the concept of justice in processes related to conflict resolution and resource allocation. It can also be used in the process used to resolve disputes or to divide benefits or responsibilities. It is also called Procedural Justice.

Researchers have conceptualized the term 'Voice of employees' in various ways (Budget al., 2010). According to Albert Hirschman (1970), the concept of Employee Voice is discussed across various disciplines, but in organizational psychology the term has gained popularity in theory buildings and behavioral implications. In his departure from office, Hirschman, while describing Voice said: Voice can be defined as an attempt to change, rather than flee into an unfavorable media situation, either by a single or joint request to the directors, by applying to the executive of actions & protests, which include those which are designed to consolidate public opinion.

The conceptual framework in this study for Procedural Fairness has been taken in terms of pay determination, pay communication, performance appraisal and appeals item. Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment has been taken in terms of the autonomy of employees in the organization.

Total of 200 questionnaires have been obtained from employees working in State Bank of India, Punjab National Bank, HDFC, ICICI in Punjab state.

The study concluded that there is a significant and positive relationship between Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment; it means that more the fairness in the procedures of the organization more will be the levels of Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment respectively. The variables like age, gender and total work experience are found to have significant relationship with Employee Voice as well as the Commitment towards the organization, whereas the type of sector in which the employee is said to be employed has no effect on them.

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The study helped in quantifying the data available for all of these three variables.

2 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1. NEED OF THE STUDY :

Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment are two vital grounds on which the productivity of the employees of the organization depends. If an employee is satisfied with his job and is committed to his organization his productivity will be more which in turn will lead to higher profitability of the organization.

Now, Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment themselves depend on a major determinant, that is, Procedural Fairness. Hence in order to keep a tap on profitability of the organization the relationship between these three variables is vital to study.

2.2 OBJECTIVES

- To study Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.
- To find out the relationship between Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice in select public and private sector banks.
- To find out the relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

3.1 HYPOTHESES

H₁ – there is high level of Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

H₂ – there is a significant relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

3.3.1 Tools for data collection :

- Procedural Fairness** - Scarpello and Jones Questionnaire, 15 items scale is used.
- Employee Voice** – Voice Behavior (Van Dyne & LePine, 1998) Questionnaire is used.
- Organizational Commitment** – Vakola and Bouradas (2003) 5 items scale is used.
- Psycho-demographic Variables** – Age, Gender, Qualification and Total Work Experience.

3.3.2 Method of data Collection :

To collect primary data to test the hypotheses a questionnaire survey was conducted. The respondents were asked to assess their perception on various items of Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and organizational commitment. Assessment was based on five point Likert scale (1- strongly disagree to 5- strongly agree).

3.3.3 Sample size – The data was collected from the employees of public sector (State Bank of Indian and Punjab National Bank) and private sector (HDFC and ICICI) banks amongst all the levels of employees of Punjab state. The sample size of the study is 200 (50 from each bank).

- Employee Voice between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment.

4. DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

H1: There is high level of Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment in public and private sector banks.

Table I: Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Procedural Fairness	200	2.63	4.48	3.7200	.43123
Employee Voice	200	2.56	4.54	3.7133	.50128
Organizational Commitment	200	2.74	4.38	3.2808	.34439
Valid N (list wise)	200				

The descriptive statistics table I above is used to show the level of Procedural, Employee Voice and the

level of Organizational Commitment. The mean of Procedural Fairness was calculated to be 3.71 and the

standard deviation stood at 0.43123 which denotes that the level of Procedural Fairness amongst the organization is above average but the data varies a lot around the mean.

The mean of Employee Voice stands at 3.7133 and the standard deviation at 0.50128 which shows an above average employees have say in the organization.

The Organizational Commitment stands averaged at 3.2808 which show a slightly below average commitment level from the employees towards the organization. Thus through the descriptive analysis it can be concluded that the three variables Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice, and Organizational Commitment show an above average level of satisfaction. Hence, hypothesis H1 is proved to be true.

According to the study it can be deduced that the three variables, i.e., Procedural Fairness, Employee Voice, and Organizational Commitment are maintained at a satisfactory level throughout the four organizations and both the sectors. It is observed here that the sectors, public as well as private, have been able to maintain an above average level of fairness regarding their

procedures and hence have gained an equal level of satisfaction and commitment from their employees. The organizations have been successful in being fair to their employees as far as their procedures like pay determination, pay communication and performance appraisal. These organizations have been open regarding their pay policy as all the information regarding the same is posted on their website which every employee using his identity card can access and the process for appraising performance is also disclosed to their employees hence they have a decent level of fairness regarding the procedures they follow. It is because of this fairness that the employees have an above average say in the organizational matters which in turn leads to commitment towards the organization. Hence the levels of Employee Voice and Organizational Commitment are above average.

H2 : There is a significant relationship between Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice in select public and private sector banks.

Table II: Correlations (Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice)

	Procedural Fairness	Employee Voice
Procedural Fairness	1	.642**
Pearson Correlation		.000
Sig. (2-tailed)		
N	200	200
Employee Voice	.642**	1
Pearson Correlation	.000	
Sig. (2-tailed)		
N	200	200

The result of Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation (table II) suggests that Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice have a strong positive correlation with each other ($r = 0.642, p = 0.00$) Procedural Fairness has a positive correlation with the Employee Voice ($r = 0.623, p = 0.00$). Since the significance level throughout all the variables is less than 0.05 and the correlation level is more than 0.05, it can be concluded that the two variables have a significant positive relationship with

each other, it can be concluded that the Null Hypothesis H2 stands to be true, i.e., there is a significant relationship between Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice.

H3: There is a significant relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

Table III: Correlations (Procedural Fairness and Organizational commitment)

		Procedural Fairness	Organizational Commitment
Procedural Fairness	Pearson Correlation	1	.460**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	200	200
Organizational Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.460**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	200	200

The result of Pearson's coefficient according to table III for Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment shows the correlation between the two to be strong and positive ($r = 0.460$, $p = 0.00$). From the above results it can so be concluded that the two variables – Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment – share a very significant positive relationship with each other as their level of significance is less than 0.05 and the Pearson's coefficient of correlation is more than 0.05. It can therefore be said that the Null Hypothesis, i.e., H3 is true, which means that Procedural Fairness as well as Organizational Commitment have a significant relationship with each other.

This study concludes that there exists a positive as well as a significant relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment. It can be

understood as if the organization is fair and transparent in its procedures regarding various areas like performance appraisal, pay determination, pay communication etc, then it will lead to building of employees' trust towards the working of the organization and hence they start believing in the way the organization works this results in the employees feeling a sense of belonging to the organization. This whole sense of belonging which they acquire leads to commitment towards the organization, that is, they want to stick around and serve the same employer rather than looking for options and shifting between organizations.

H4: Employee Voice mediates the relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

TABLE IV: STEPWISE REGRESSION ANALYSIS (MEDIATION ANALYSIS OF EMPLOYEE VOICE BETWEEN PROCEDURAL FAIRNESS AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT)

Model Summary		R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	
1		.857 ^a	.734	.734	.7402808	
2		.881 ^b	.777	.776	.6786059	
ANOVA TABLE		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	698.963	1	698.963	1.275E3	.000 ^a
	Residual	253.183	99	.548		
	Total	952.146	200			
2	Regression	739.853	2	369.926	803.304	.000 ^b
	Residual	212.293	98	.461		
	Total	952.146	200			

COEFFICIENTS	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.299	.076		3.953	.000
Procedural Fairness	.905	.025	.857	35.713	.000
2 (Constant)	.201	.070		2.878	.004
Procedural Fairness	.518	.047	.490	10.982	.000
Employee Voice	.540	.057	.421	9.423	.000

a. Predictors: Procedural Fairness and Employee Voice

b. Dependent Variable: Organizational Commitment

Table IV of stepwise regression analysis shows that with the insertion of the variable Employee Voice, the strength of the relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment increases at significant level. Hence the hypothesis H4 stands true.

From this study it can be concluded that Employee Voice mediates the relationship between Procedural Fairness and Organizational Commitment in select public and private sector banks.

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